

CARDIOCARE: An integrated platform for the management of elderly multimorbid patients with breast cancer therapy induced cardiac toxicity

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Abstract— Breast cancer (BC) remains the most diagnosed cancer in women, accounting for 12% of new annual cancer cases in Europe and worldwide. Advances in surgery, radiotherapy and systemic treatment have resulted in improved clinical outcomes and increased survival rates in recent years. However, BC therapy-related cardiotoxicity, may severely impact short- and long-term quality of life and survival. This study presents the CARDIOCARE platform and its main components, which by integrating patient- specific data from different categories, data from patient-oriented eHealth applications and wearable devices, and by employing advanced data mining and machine learning approaches, provides the healthcare professionals with a valuable tool for effectively managing BC patients and preventing or alleviating treatment induced cardiotoxicity.

Clinical Relevance— Through the adoption of CARDIOCARE platform healthcare professionals are able to stratify patients for their risk for cardiotoxicity and timely apply adequate interventions to prevent its onset.

I. INTRODUCTION

Recent advances in early cancer detection and therapy have dramatically changed the natural course of many cancer types transforming them into chronic diseases. Due to a strong

reduction in cancer mortality, it is estimated that there will be more than 22 million cancer survivors by 2026 and approximately two-thirds of all cancer survivors will be older than 65 years [1]. However, the success on improving cancer survival has been compromised by the short, or long-term collateral adverse effects caused by cancer therapies. Among several side effects of cancer treatment, cardiotoxicity has emerged as a major cause of co-morbidity and mortality in cancer patients, which further impairs their physical, psychosocial status and Quality of Life (QoL) [2].

Cardiotoxicity is one of the most devastating adverse outcomes of chemotherapy, resulting in a significant increase of morbidity and mortality rates [3]. Cardiotoxicity may occur in the initial or late phases of disease evolution and can take different forms, from myocardial dysfunction to heart failure or even death. In fact, cardiomyopathy and heart failure, detected as left ventricular dysfunction, are two of the most common clinical manifestations of cardiotoxic adverse effects induced by cancer therapy [4]. However, cardiotoxicity due to cancer therapy may manifest itself in many other forms including, such as hypertension, arrhythmias, valvular and coronary artery disease. The onset of cardiotoxicity can occur at different timepoints and can be classified as acute (during

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therapy), early progressive (within one year of therapy) and late progressive cardiotoxicity (greater than one year of therapy) [5]. Contemporary cancer treatments comprising chemotherapy (anthracyclines, alkylating agents) and monoclonal antibodies, have been associated with increased risk for cardiotoxicity [6]. With 3 to 4 million cancer patients diagnosed each year in Europe and with female BC being the most frequent cancer (reaching 523,000 new cases in 2018), there is an increased risk for BC therapy-related complications [7]. Indeed, BC patients undergoing treatment have been the focus of intense research, since cardiotoxicity frequently affects these patients reducing life expectancy and QoL, significantly [8].

This study presents a beyond the state-of-the-art interdisciplinary platform, developed in the framework of CARDIOCARE project [9], used for the management of the elderly multimorbid patient with BC therapy induced cardiac toxicity. The innovation of CARDIOCARE relies upon the delivery of a holistic approach for managing BC patients, integrating a patient-oriented eHealth mobile application and wearable devices, retrospective and prospective clinical data and employing advanced data mining and machine learning approaches for the creation of risk stratification models of cardiotoxicity.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Retrospective data

During the project lifecycle, retrospective data from 1560 BC patients will be collected (Table I).

TABLE I. RETROSPECTIVE DATA CATEGORIES.

	IEO	BOCOC	KSBC	NKUA	UOI
No of patients	300	600	260	300	100
Cardiac Imaging	Echocardiogram, Electrocardiography (Every 3 months at treatment)				
Biomarkers	Troponin I	N/A			
	B-type natriuretic peptide				
Psychomarkers	Platelet, Fibrinogen, C-Reactive Protein	N/A	Platelets inflammation markers	N/A	
Blood samples	Available from all centers				
Quality of Life (QoL)	Distress thermometer	QoL information (from patient monitoring)		N/A	
	EORTC-QLQ Questionnaire				
Breast Imaging	Mammography	Mammography, Ultrasound guided biopsy			
	Computed Tomography				
Tissue	Biopsy tissue				

The 5 clinical centers involved in the retrospective data collection are the European Institute of Oncology (IEO), the Bank of Cyprus Oncology Centre (BOCOC), the Karolinska University Hospital (KSBC), the National and Kapodistrian

University of Athens (NKUA) and the University of Ioannina (UOI). Currently data from 1432 out of 1560 cases have been collected. These data belong to different categories including: (i) Cardiac imaging data, (ii) Biomarker data, (iii) Psychomarkers data, (iv) Blood examination data, (v) QoL data, (vi) Breast imaging data and, (vii) Tissue data.

B. Prospective clinical study

Currently cardio-oncology guidelines recommend that serial examinations, electrocardiogram (ECGs), echocardiograms, circulating biomarkers (e.g. Troponin I, B-type natriuretic peptide) and detailed assessment of the intrinsic capacity of the individuals, defined as the composite of all physical and mental capacities (Integrated Care for Older People – ICOPE guidelines [10]), have to be included in a standard follow-up protocol to establish optimal practices for the management of the elderly BC patient at risk of cardiotoxic adverse effects. In this perspective, CARDIOCARE platform, together with biological information, is monitoring psychological, emotional and functional information to be used as informative markers of the risk for cardiotoxicity. Particularly, the CARDIOCARE prospective clinical study involves clinical, genomic, biochemical, and imaging (echocardiography, mammography) procedures, sensor monitoring of health status and utilization of the CARDIOCARE mobile application.

The study involves 6 recruitment centers located in Europe; IEO, BOCOC, KSBC, UOI, NKUA, and Onkoloski Institut Ljubljana [11] (IOL). The number of patients to be enrolled per clinical center, in a 12-month recruiting period, is: (i) *IEO*: 125 patients, (ii) *BOCOC*: 120 patients, (iii) *KSBC*: 125 patients, (iv) *UOI*: 60 patients, (v) *NKUA*: 195 patients, and (vi) *IOL*: 125 patients. Of the 750 patients, 375 will be included in the control group (only monitoring) and 375 will be included in the intervention group

C. Sensor Devices

D. Omics – An innovative approach for predicting cardiotoxicity after cancer treatment

Omics technologies offer a unique insight into the molecular level mechanisms that may drive the observed cardiotoxicity following cancer treatment. Differences in the development of cardiotoxicity after treatment, may be attributable to genetic variation. Several genetic biomarkers are known to be associated with BC predisposition, and disease progress, however very few are hypothesized to be linked to cardiotoxicity following cancer treatment. The CARDIOCARE platform integrates novel omics technologies (genomics, transcriptomics, and metagenomics) for the study of cardiotoxicity in BC patients. In particular, we focus on genetic biomarkers in genes relevant to drug metabolism as potential contributions to variations in drug exposure and subsequent development of cardiotoxicity. These biomarkers are expected to define new approaches for prognostic identification of patients who are at increased risk of cardiotoxicity following chemotherapy.

Another -omics data modality, miRNA's, provide the opportunity to study the byproduct of activated biological mechanisms of interest. Unlike genetic biomarkers, miRNA biomarkers can be used to identify if specific biological mechanisms are active at a specific point in time. Following a systematic literature review of microRNAs as potential biomarkers of chemotherapy induced cardiotoxicity in BC patients, we determined a strategy for testing several candidate miRNAs [13] (Table II). In addition, this literature review also revealed that CARDIOCARE is the largest study of its kind to consider miRNAs meeting statistical power requirements and therefore expected to reveal potentially true positive effects.

TABLE II. IDENTIFIED PANELS OF INFORMATIVE MICRORNA'S FOR CHEMOTHERAPY-INDUCED CARDIOTOXICITY IN BC PATIENTS.

miRNAs			
Cardiotoxicity	DOX	EC-D/NAC	EC-D + T
miR-29a	miR-1	miR-17	miR-130a
miR-34a	miR-122	miR-19a	
miR-423	miR-499	miR-199	
		miR-378	

An important potential contributor to the differences in risk for cardiotoxicity in BC undergoing treatment, addressed in CARDIOCARE, is the gut microbiome. Recent advances in genetic sequences have enabled the targeted genetic regions on the 16s protein of bacteria to identify them. This results in the identification of the type of bacteria growing in a fecal sample, as well as the relative abundance of each across all taxonomy levels down to genus with high accuracy, and species for some organisms.

E. eHealth mobile application

CARDIOCARE mobile suite incorporates two sub-applications: (i) the *ePsyncHeart mobile application* (Figure 1), and (ii) the *eHealthHeart mobile application* (Figure 2). Patients in the control arm of the clinical study have at their disposal the ePsyncHeart mobile application, while patients in the intervention arm use both the ePsyncHeart and eHealthHeart mobile applications. The end users of both applications are patients and the caregivers.

The ePsyncHeart mobile application (Fig. 1) coupled with wearable sensors (smartwatch, heart zone sensor) and the hand grip dynamometer allows the consistent evaluation and monitoring of patients' intrinsic capacity towards improving their QoL and assisting in their selfcare and self-management. The application includes the following modules: (i) *Sensors & IoT Module*, which collects user data from all the wearable sensors, to be further analyzed. It includes the *Locomotion Module*, which collects and visualizes data from the smartwatch regarding the user's physical activity and the *Vital Condition Module*, which collects and visualizes data from the heart zone sensor regarding the user's heart functionality. (ii) *PROMs/PREMs & Questionnaires Module*, which collects and visualizes data from questionnaires and includes the *QoL Module*, which analyzes the user's responses from completed questionnaires to evaluate their QoL. In brief, the patients are asked to fill in 14 questionnaires (e.g. Anxiety and Depression (PHQ4) questionnaire [14], Quality of life (EORTC-QLQ-30/BR23 [15]) questionnaire, etc.) to assess their psychological and behavioral status. The eHealthHeart mobile

application targets at improving patients' intrinsic capacity, including psychological empowerment, cognitive stimulation, physical activity, assess vision and hearing status, and assist in dietary and management of urinary incontinence. This is achieved by the utilization of the Psychological Support Module, the Cognitive Stimulation Module, the Geriatric Syndromes assessment Module, the Dietary Nutrition Module, the Vision and Hearing Module. In addition, there exists the Education and Training Module, which provides information for psychological and social support, training, and education.

Figure 1. *ePsyncHeart mobile application* and main modules.

Figure 2. *eHealthHeart mobile application* and main modules.

F. Integrated risk stratification model of cardiotoxicity

The image- and the non-image based risk stratification models are unified in a separate model (integrated risk stratification model of cardiotoxicity), capable of enhancing the early diagnosis and management of cardiotoxicity.

Risk stratification model of cardiotoxicity based on imaging data. The image-based risk stratification model exploits echocardiography images to identify new quantitative imaging biomarkers and signatures predictive of cardiotoxicity and patient response. The design and the implementation stage of the model consists of image processing algorithms suitable for extracting various features (shape, size, text etc.) related to subtle and/or complex predictive signals.

Risk stratification model of cardiotoxicity based on non-imaging data. Using non-imaging data, the application of machine learning techniques allows the development of a risk prediction model for predicting cardiotoxicity. Specifically, the non-imaging data include Electronic Health Records, lab tests, circulating biomarkers (e.g Troponins, BNP) and other data coming from the mobile applications (psychomarkers, questionnaires, physical activity, nutrition, etc). Omics biomarkers (SNPs, miRNAs, gut microbiome) are also included as an additional input.

G. The Infrastructure

The CARDIOCARE platform (Fig. 3) is developed and delivered based on several best-of-breed open-source technologies. At its core, the platform can support the management of the collected data in ways that make cross-

sectional and longitudinal data integration possible. Data is entering the platform through a variety of means, e.g., through batch upload (retrospective data), streams (e.g. sensor data), manual entry, etc. Upon entry, data are harmonized to a common data model with the proper concept mapping and subject (patient) identification and linking, and then stored on the platform's specialized repositories for quick retrieval and summarization. The platform itself is deployed on a Kubernetes enabled cluster of hardware resources that offers virtualized and containerized monitoring and load balancing services. The managed data can then be processed by a multitude of tools and services to support visualization, cohort creation, analytics, and knowledge extraction through the development of data mining and machine learning models (risk stratification model of cardiotoxicity).

Figure 3. CARDIOCARE platform overview.

III. CONCLUSION

In this study, CARDIOCARE, an integrated platform, for the management of elderly multimorbid patients with BC therapy induced cardiac toxicity, has been presented. To the best of our knowledge, such a holistic approach for stratifying the risk of cardiotoxicity in BC patients, integrating patient-specific data, data from eHealth applications and wearable devices, and data mining and machine learning approaches is not existing, an innovation expected to be validated with records from 1560 retrospective and 750 prospective BC patients in 6 clinical centers.

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